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URBAN ROADSIDE TOPSOIL–SUBSOIL NUTRIENTS UNDER THE CANOPY OF *TERMINALIA MANTALY*: RELATIONSHIPS AMONG TREE GROWTH, BIOMASS, AND SOIL QUALITY INDICATORS

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Abstract: *The study examined urban roadside topsoil–subsoil nutrients under the canopy of Terminalia mantaly, as well as the relationships among tree growth, biomass, and soil quality indicators. Using a transect line approach, soil samples were collected under the canopy of each tree at a horizontal distance of 1 m from the tree base in the topsoil and subsoil. The soil nutrients were subsequently analyzed in the laboratory. Diameter at breast height, tree height, and canopy were measured using standard procedures, while aboveground and belowground biomass was estimated using allometric equations. Data were statistically analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics (Student's t-test and Pearson's product–moment correlation). The study revealed that higher values of sand, silt, total porosity, pH, cation exchange capacity, soil organic matter (SOM), total organic carbon (TOC), total nitrogen, available phosphorus, calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg), and potassium were observed in the topsoil, while clay, bulk density, and sodium were higher in the subsoil. Significant differences between the two soil depths were detected only for sand, clay, SOM, TOC, Ca, and Mg. Significant relationships were observed among tree growth, biomass, and soil quality indicators at both soil depths. The findings further revealed that tree growth and biomass are more strongly related to subsoil properties than to topsoil properties. The study concluded that the differences in soil quality indicators' levels between the soil depths are attributed to the effects of anthropogenic activities along the roadside and the canopy, and that the subsoil plays a stronger role in the tree species' growth and development.*

Keywords: Biomass, Soil nutrients, Tree growth, *Terminalia mantaly*, Urban soils

INTRODUCTION

Terminalia mantaly (umbrella tree) is a plant species indigenous to Madagascar, but introduced as an exotic species to Tanzania, Zambia, Nigeria, Zimbabwe, Kenya, Senegal, Somalia, Uganda, Ethiopia, Djibouti, and Eritrea (Babalola & Raji, 2016; Yunusa et al., 2024). It is an evergreen tree, predominantly found in tropical and subtropical regions, belongs to the family Combretaceae, and is well known for its ethnobotanical and economic significance (Owoade & Oke,

2020). *Terminalia mantaly* is also an ornamental avenue tree widely planted along streets, roads, parks, residential areas, religious centers, and schools. Its extensive use in urban landscapes in contemporary times reveals a strong perception of its environmental and ecological value, predominantly in urban greening and restoration initiatives (Adedeji et al., 2022).

Studies on *Terminalia mantaly* have predominantly focused on its medicinal uses. These investigations include evaluations of

phytochemical composition, antioxidant activity, and antibacterial properties (Ebele et al., 2021; Yunusa et al., 2024), as well as investigations of antiplasmodial and antimalarial activities against *Plasmodium falciparum* (Samuel & Adekunle, 2021; Usman et al., 2022). Other research has examined ethnomedicinal mapping and assessment of the species in built-up areas (Eludoyin et al., 2015), its potential as a new host for the tropical Tasar silkworm *Antheraea mylitta* Drury (Lepidoptera: Saturniidae) (Kavane & Chougale, 2024), and its carbon sequestration potentials (Orobator & Adahwara, 2022).

Soil quality is soil- and site-specific (Kamal et al., 2023), and soil nutrient status and distribution are affected by soil depth (Teramage et al., 2023). Soil depth plays an important role in nutrient distribution and organic matter retention, as surface layers usually contain higher soil organic matter (SOM) and nutrient concentrations than deeper layers (Hamza et al., 2025). Understanding how soil depths interact to influence soil quality is vital for developing sustainable soil management strategies. Soil depth also plays a significant role in soil-vegetation relationship. Studies have defined this important aspect of soil-vegetation relationships as a “nutrient pump” (van Noordwijk & Purnomosidhi, 1995) because the trees extract nutrients from the soil depths for usage, and subsequently release them to the topsoil through litter deposition. The soil-vegetation relationship is multifaceted: soil provides physical support and nutrients necessary for plant growth, while vegetation contributes to soil nutrient pools through nutrient cycling. Vegetation and soil are functionally inter-reliant and exert symbiotic influences on one another (Aweto, 1981a). Vegetation is not only an indispensable factor of soil formation; the nature of vegetation in a

region also provides an insight into soil conditions (Ogunkunle, 2013).

Globally, studies on soil-vegetation interrelationships suggest that research focusing specifically on *Terminalia mantaly* remains limited, as existing investigations have largely examined other forest types and tree species. For example, previous studies have explored relationships between soil properties and vegetation at the Northern Experimental Forest in Maine (Levine et al., 1994), soil-vegetation relationships in forest biogeocenoses using principal component analysis (Koptsik et al., 2003), correlations between forest soil quality and aboveground vegetation characteristics in China (Shen et al., 2022), soil-landscape-vegetation relationships at grassland-forest boundaries (Redin et al., 2023), and vegetation-soil coupling across desert ecosystems in China (Han et al., 2025).

In addition, research in Nigeria has examined vegetation gradients and soil variables in mangrove swamps (Ukpong & Areola, 1995); soil-vegetation interrelationships in *Isobertinia* woodlands of northwestern Nigeria (Ubom & Isichei, 1995); soil-vegetation interrelationships in secondary forests using multivariate analyses (Iwara, 2011); canonical correlation applications in the cocoa belt of south-western Nigeria (Ekanade & Orimoogunje, 2012); soil-vegetation relationships in secondary forests regenerating on degraded rubber plantations (Ichikogu, 2014); soil and vegetation dynamics in bush-fallow systems of the derived savanna (Odegbaro & Aweto, 2017); soil properties under *Parkia biglobosa* canopies in relation to tree biomass on farmland (Alo & Aweto, 2018); and correlations between plant biomass and soil attributes under bush mango and lowland rainforest trees (Ndakara, 2024).

Cities are considered as one of centers of high flora diversity with an exclusively large number of non-native tree species (Wang & López-Pujol, 2015). Trees are strategic components of the urban ecosystems, providing shade and supporting biodiversity (Qi, 2024), and urban soil quality is an important factor for the growth and development of trees (Hilbert et al., 2019). Urban soils in roadside tree systems, which provide permeable substrates adjacent to impervious urban surfaces such as asphalt and cement, play a significant role as growth media for urban trees (Guilland et al., 2018). Roadsides are a type of informal green space within urban areas that are often overlooked or examined only in terms of their environmental impacts (Säumel et al., 2016). Studies on urban roadside soils have largely focused on heavy metal contamination with vehicular emissions and industrial activities identified as major sources (Ekpenkhio et al., 2025; Orobator & Daniel, 2025). Research on urban roadsides topsoil-subsoil nutrients under the canopy of urban trees, and on growth, biomass, and soil quality relationships, remain comparatively scarce. Urban trees differ in their nutrient requirements and tolerance levels across soil depths, making it imperative to understand the topsoil-subsoil dynamics of soil nutrients distribution.

To fill the identified gaps, this study adopted a soil profile approach to quantitatively examine urban roadside topsoil and subsoil nutrients under the canopy of *Terminalia mantaly* in the Benin region of South-South Nigeria. It further examined the relationships among soil quality indicators, tree growth and

biomass parameters. In this research, soil depths (topsoil and subsoil) served as the spatial gradients for assessing depth-specific soil-plant interactions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY AREA

This study was carried out along the Benin–Ogba Road in Benin City, which is located between latitudes 6°19'12.0" and 6°14'24.0" and longitudes 5°36'0.0" and 5°40'.48" E in the southern part of Edo State, Nigeria (Figure 1). For ease of spatial analysis, Benin City was first divided into two equal halves along a longitudinal axis. Based on this scientific sampling model, the researcher purposively selected the northeast–south zonal half, which contains major arterial roads such as the Benin–Lagos Road, Benin–Siluko Road, Benin–Ekenhuan Road, and Benin–Ogba Road. Subsequently, through randomization and based on the incidence of *Terminalia mantaly* trees, Benin–Ogba Road popularly known as Airport Road was selected as the study site. Atewe and Asikhia (2025) reported that Benin–Ogba Road is a significant arterial route within metropolitan Benin. Benin City experiences a tropical rainforest climate, and the soils are predominantly ferrallitic, characterized by a yellowish-brown coloration. A reconnaissance survey conducted in Benin City indicated that urban forestry is not a prominent feature along major road corridors. The survey also showed that the Benin–Ogba Road was the only major arterial road along which *Terminalia mantaly* trees were planted, although only in a few sections.

Figure 1: Location of the study site
Source: EdoGIS, Modified by the authors

FIELD MEASUREMENTS, SAMPLING PROCEDURES, AND BIOMASS ESTIMATION

During the fieldwork, sampling was conducted using a systematic line transect method along a road. The road served as the transect line, along which eight (8) *Terminalia mantaly* trees planted at 20 m intervals were

selected as sampling points. Soil samples were collected beneath the canopy of each *Terminalia mantaly* tree at a horizontal distance of 1 m from the tree base, at depths of 0–15 cm and 15–30 cm, representing the topsoil and subsoil, respectively (Adejuwon & Adesina, 1990). Consequently, a total of sixteen (16) soil samples were obtained for the study. The 1 m sampling distance was adopted

to allow the soil auger to penetrate the soil profile from the topsoil to the subsoil with minimal interference from tree roots. Sampling at these depth intervals also facilitated the assessment of the vertical distribution of soil nutrients within the soil profile. The growth parameters measured for the sampled *Terminalia mantaly* trees included diameter at breast height (DBH), tree height (TH), and tree canopy (TC). The DBH was measured at 1.3 m above ground level using a diameter tape, while tree height (TH) was measured following the procedures adopted by Ichikogu (2014), in which the angle to the top of each tree and the horizontal distance from the observation point was measured using an Abney level and a measuring tape, respectively.

Consequently, tree height was calculated using the formula

$$H = X \tan \Theta$$

Where

H = Height of tree

X = Distance of observer from tree

Θ = Angle of tree top from observer

Tree canopy (TC) was measured using the crown diameter method, by measuring two perpendicular crown diameters and calculating their mean (Avery & Burkhart, 2002). The aboveground tree biomass (AGTB) was estimated using the allometric equation proposed by Chave et al., (2005) (Eq.1).

$$AGTB = 0.0509 * pD^2 H \quad (1).$$

Where; AGTB = aboveground tree biomass (kg), p = wood specific gravity ($g\ cm^{-3}$), D = diameter at breast height (cm), and H = tree height (m). The wood specific gravity for *Terminalia mantaly* tree is $0.79\ g\ cm^{-3}$. Belowground biomass (BGB) estimation was undertaken using root-to-shoot ratio value of

1:5, which is 20% of the total aboveground tree biomass (Miller et al., 2006) (Eq.2).

$$BGB = 0.2 \times AGTB \quad (2).$$

SOIL LABORATORY ANALYSIS

The hydrometer method was adopted to determine sand, silt, and clay (Gee & Or, 2002). BD was determined using a soil core and driving a manual hammer probe, and drying the soil at $105^{\circ}C$ for 24h to determine the soil dry weight contained in the soil volume (Kim & Yoo, 2020). To determine Total Porosity (TP), the particle density was measured using the pycnometer method, and BD was determined from oven-dried soil cores; TP was then calculated from these values. Total nitrogen, total organic carbon, available phosphorus, and exchangeable bases were determined following the procedures described by Begum et al., (2010). To obtain SOM, the SOC values were by multiplying by a factor of 1.724 (Aweto, 1981b).

STATISTICAL ANALYZES

The statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23. Mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variation, and range were calculated for all the examined soil nutrients to summarize their central tendencies and variability. A Student's t-test was used to test for significant differences in soil nutrients between soil profiles spatial gradients (topsoil and subsoil). Pearson correlation analysis was used to determine the relationships among tree growth characteristics, biomass, and soil quality indicators for each soil depth. Soil nutrients values were compared against permissible limits to determine their status.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

CHARACTERISTICS OF TOPSOIL–SUBSOIL NUTRIENTS

The descriptive statistics of the nutrients of the topsoil and subsoil, as well as the p-values obtained from the results of the Student’s t-test analysis are presented in Table 1. The concentrations of sand (736.88 g kg⁻¹) and silt (160.00 g kg⁻¹) were higher in the topsoil, whereas the subsoil had a higher bulk density (143.75 g kg⁻¹). This revealed that sand and silt contents decreased with increasing soil depth from the topsoil to the subsoil, while clay increased with depth; however, only sand and clay across the depths were significantly different (p < 0.05). The higher sand and silt contents observed in the topsoil may be attributed to the deposition of non-exhaust

emissions. These emissions consist of particles generated by vehicle tires abrasion, brake linings, and road surfaces, as well as the degradation of other vehicle components (He et al., 2024). The observed decrease in silt may also be due to the dominant influence of sand-forming minerals in parent materials (Kamal et al., 2023), and may indicate that weathering is more in the subsoil than the topsoil (Nwosu et al., 2025). The increase in clay in the subsoil could be ascribed to the translocation of clay particles from the topsoil to subsoil layers through the processes of eluviation and illuviation (Jimoh et al., 2020), which eventually leads to increased concentrations of sand and silt in the topsoil layers (Mengistu et al., 2017). This aligned with the findings of Kurniawan et al. (2019) who observed that clay content was greater in the subsoil than topsoil.

Table 1: Summary of Topsoil and Subsoil Nutrients

Soil properties	Topsoil				Subsoil				p-value
	Range	Mean	SD	CV (%)	Range	Mean	SD	CV (%)	
Sand (gkg ⁻¹)	650.00 - 800.00	736.88	60.29	8.18	600.00 - 800.00	706.25	56.30	7.97	0.03*
Silt (gkg ⁻¹)	80.00 - 250.00	160.00	72.31	45.19	50.00 - 200.00	150.00	59.76	39.84	0.32
Clay (gkg ⁻¹)	5.00 - 250.00	103.13	75.92	73.62	100.00 - 250.00	143.75	56.30	39.16	0.03*
BD (Mg m ⁻³)	1.25 - 1.66	1.48	0.16	10.89	1.25 - 1.66	1.50	0.12	7.94	0.28
TP (%)	37.35 - 52.83	44.19	6.08	13.76	37.35 - 55.83	43.49	4.49	10.32	0.28
pH	5.06 - 7.50	6.22	0.73	11.73	4.97 - 7.26	6.09	0.80	13.16	0.24
CEC (cmol kg ⁻¹)	14.90 - 34.30	26.51	7.27	27.43	14.90 - 30.81	23.10	6.60	28.59	0.10
TOC (gkg ⁻¹)	1.74 - 8.13	5.16	1.93	37.35	1.74 - 5.23	3.19	1.24	38.93	0.01*
SOM (gkg ⁻¹)	3.00 - 14.00	8.88	3.31	37.34	3.00 - 9.00	5.50	2.14	38.87	0.01*
TN (gkg ⁻¹)	0.19 - 0.39	0.31	0.06	20.76	0.24 - 0.35	0.29	0.04	13.79	0.26
Aval. P (mg kg ⁻¹)	5.62 - 14.33	9.87	3.21	32.52	3.63 - 14.33	8.50	3.56	41.90	0.25
Ca (cmol kg ⁻¹)	1.24 - 3.40	2.12	0.75	35.53	1.04 - 1.89	1.58	0.28	17.89	0.05*
Na (cmol kg ⁻¹)	1.01 - 1.97	1.50	0.32	21.42	1.20 - 2.57	1.83	0.50	27.65	0.10
K (cmol kg ⁻¹)	11.30 - 29.66	22.49	7.14	31.76	10.15 - 26.29	19.40	6.64	34.24	0.11

Source: Authors’ Fieldwork, 2025

BD increased with soil depth, from the topsoil (1.48 Mg m^{-3}) to the subsoil (1.50 Mg m^{-3}); however, the difference was not statistically significant. These BD values may be due to external compressive force such as human trampling (Jim & Ng, 2018). The higher BD in the subsoil may be ascribed to its higher clay content. Nonetheless, since the BD values for both soil depths fall within the permissible limit ($\leq 1.5 \text{ Mg m}^{-3}$), they are unlikely to have adverse effects on tree growth. Generally, a BD above 1.6 Mg/m^3 is considered as obstructive to tree root development (Craul & Patterson, 1989), even though Craul and Klein (1980) reported that tree roots can extend through avenues of weakness in the soil up to 1.68 Mg/m^3 . However, the BD of the examined urban roadside soils indicated that they are marginally affected by human influences, as the values fall within the range of $1.4\text{--}1.6 \text{ Mg m}^{-3}$ (Jim & Ng, 2018). Human activities such as pedestrian traffic and the paving of hard surfaces influence urban soils, thereby distinguishing them from soils of other biomes such as forests and savannahs (Joimel et al., 2016). Higher TP was obtained at 0-15 cm with a value of 44.19 % and lowest at 15-30 cm with a value of 43.49 %. These TP values demonstrated that the urban roadside soils were slightly affected by anthropogenic impacts (Jim & Ng, 2018). The higher TP in the topsoil is also indicative of the incidence of higher SOM (8.88 gkg^{-1}). Investigations have revealed that the presence of SOM enhances high porosity, which can promote soil water retention and soil fertility and improve tree growth (Norris et al., 2014). Conversely, the lower porosity in the subsoil may indicate the higher incidence of clay particles (143.75 Mg m^{-3}). The observed TP values at both soil depths may not be adequate to sustain and regulate soil ecosystem activity or to improve good water infiltration and aeration, as they were below the recommended TP threshold of about 50% and above (Landon, 1991). However, the TP

values would also not be considered harmful to aeration, moisture transmission, and root growth, since they were not below the critical limit of 40% (Haan & van der Valk, 1970).

Soil pH decreased with increasing soil depth from 0–15 (6.22) to 15–30cm (6.09). Traffic activities, especially road abrasion, strongly influence the pH of roadside soils (Werkenthin, 2014). The decrease through soil depth could also be attributed to lower concentrations of basic cations (Ca, Mg, and K) in the subsoil, resulting in a lower pH in the subsurface soil. The higher pH in the topsoil layer could be due to the accumulation of Ca, Mg, and K. However, the decrease in pH with increasing soil depths could be ascribed to the leaching of basic cations and the lower SOM in the subsoil compared to the topsoil (Kamal et al., 2023). The interaction between depths for soil pH was not significant ($p > 0.05$). The findings of the current study are similar with the report of (Kamal et al., 2023). The pH values at both soil depths were slightly acidic, but fell within the permissible range of 6.0–7.5, which is considered appropriate for most crops. The concentrations of CEC ($26.51 \text{ cmol kg}^{-1}$) were higher in the topsoil than in the subsoil had a ($23.10 \text{ cmol kg}^{-1}$). CEC demonstrated the soil's capacity to retain nutrients in the form of exchangeable cations (Mashagiro et al., 2024), while soil leaching and low concentrations of basic cations may account for observed differences in CEC (Akinde et al., 2020).

Higher concentrations of TOC, SOM, and TN were observed in the topsoil compared to the subsoil; however, only TOC and SOM varied significantly with soil depth ($p < 0.05$). Urban soils are prone to direct littering, thus increasing organic matter in the topsoil (Sager, 2020). Besides, the higher SOM in the topsoil compared to the subsoil may be due to litterfall and the decomposition of the biomass of *Terminalia mantaly*. The higher TOC in the

topsoil relative to the subsoil could be attributed to its position in the soil profile, which allows direct input of organic litter (Sahrawat, 2004). Similarly, Mafuyai et al., (2015) reported that the high TOC along Bauchi Ring Road (BRR) reveals the distribution of vegetation and grasses along the road. The higher TN in the topsoil may be ascribed to active decomposition processes in the surface layer (Nwosu et al., 2025) and reflects its strong association with SOM, with more than 75% of TN derived from organic matter (Ubuoh et al., 2013). The value of TN content in soil under tree canopy may be ascribed largely to its restitution to the soil through litter fall (Parthiban & Rai, 1994). Based on permissible limits by Arifin et al. (2012), TOC and TN were within moderately adequate levels of 1–5 g kg⁻¹ and 0.1–0.5 g kg⁻¹, respectively. Given the truncation of the topsoil layer and inadequate replenishment of organic litter under most roadside conditions (Jim, 1998), the observed moderate status of TOC and TN may majorly be attributed to the effects of litterfall and decomposition processes associated with *Terminalia mantaly*.

The observed higher Avail. P in topsoil may be triggered by human-induced activities, including the brake residues, tire wear, and deposition of exhaust (Qin et al., 2019). Furthermore, the higher Avail. P in the topsoil indicated the incidence of higher SOM which demonstrates the important contribution of the SOM content to the phosphorus pool of soils (Isola et al., 2020). Among the exchangeable cations, except Na, the concentrations of Ca, Mg, and K decreased with increasing soil depth. The decrease in Ca, Mg, and K could be credited to the absorption of nutrient by the tree plant in the topsoil, as well as the

observed decrease in SOC from the topsoil to subsoil (Yahqub et al., 2024). This may be due to soil SOC being described to be a storehouse and pool of plant nutrients (Young, 2000). Conversely, the increase in Na with soil depth could be ascribed to weathering of parent materials and its accrual in the subsoil (Demessie et al., 2011). Na concentrations are found in roads owing to the slow discharge of halite compounds from the subsoils (Sager, 2020). Similarly, Gallardo (2003) reported a lower concentration of Na under the holm oak canopy. Only the interaction between depths for Ca and Mg was significant ($p < 0.05$). Based on permissible limits (Arifin et al., 2012), Mg was low (< 0.42 cmol kg⁻¹), indicative of possible deficiencies; Ca was moderate (0.51–5.00 cmol kg⁻¹), and K was high (> 4.17 cmol kg⁻¹), suggestive of an excellent exchangeable reserve.

Two key causal factors that may be attributed to the buildup of nutrients on the topsoil under the tree canopy are the interception of the rain by the tree canopy which reduces the intensity of leaching of soil nutrients under the trees, and the activities of Annelids (earthworms) which leads to the accretion of more earthworm casts under the trees, mostly during the wet season (Alo & Aweto, 2018). In addition, litterfall from the *Terminalia mantaly* canopy plays a significant role in the accretion of nutrients in the topsoil.

GROWTH, BIOMASS, AND SOIL QUALITY INDICATOR RELATIONSHIPS

The examined *Terminalia mantaly* growth parameters (tree height, diameter at breast height, and tree canopy) and biomass parameters (aboveground and belowground biomass) are discussed here (Table 2).

Table 2. Summary of tree growth and biomass parameters of *Terminalia mantaly* trees

Tree no.	Tree Height (m)	DBH (cm)	Tree canopy (m)	AGTB (kg/tree)	BGB (kg/tree)
1	7.32	15.30	12.80	68.90	13.78
2	19.50	16.00	13.38	200.73	40.15
3	10.20	15.30	14.67	96.01	19.20
4	9.30	13.00	13.00	63.10	12.64
5	10.04	17.00	13.32	116.67	23.33
6	10.34	16.20	12.05	109.12	21.82
7	9.52	15.30	12.21	89.61	17.92
8	15.13	17.00	12.81	175.83	35.17
	$\bar{x} = 11.42$	$\bar{x} = 156.40$	$\bar{x} = 13.03$	$\bar{x} = 114.99$	$\bar{x} = 23.00$

Note: \bar{x} =Mean

Source: Authors' Fieldwork, 2025

The height of *Terminalia mantaly* trees ranged from 9.3 to 19.5 m, with a mean of 11.42 m. The mean tree height suggested that the trees are matured and have likely been growing in soils for several decades, allowing them to exert impacts on the soil beneath their canopies (Alo & Aweto, 2018), and suggested a superior capability for light acquisition (Ononyume & Edu, 2025). The variation in the tree height highpoints species-specific differences in vertical growth potential (Ononyume & Edu, 2025). In contrast, Panthi et al. (2022) reported lower tree height values in the Chure forest areas of Arghakhanchi District, Nepal. DBH ranged from 130 to 170 cm, with a mean of 156.40 cm. The DBH exhibited by the *Terminalia mantaly* trees demonstrated a higher radial growth capability, potentially owing to its species-specific physiology (Chen et al., 2022). The observed range of DBH differed from that reported by Edmondson et al. (2014) in their study on urban tree effects on soil organic carbon. They reported a DBH range from 2.5 cm to 197 cm.

The values of the tree canopy diameter ranged from 12.05 m to 14.67 m, with a mean of 13.03 m, suggesting that the *Terminalia mantaly* trees are moderately large. In forest ecology, Spurr and Barnes (1980) indicated that tree canopy diameters in the range of 12–15 m are often associated with mature or near-mature trees growing under conditions of moderate to low competition. This interpretation is consistent with the present study, as the *Terminalia mantaly* trees were planted along the roadside at approximately 20 m spacing, which likely reduced competition and allowed for tree crown expansion. The values of the AGTB ranged from 63.10 to 200.73 kg/tree, with a mean of 114.99 kg/tree. The relatively high mean value implies that medium-to-large trees contribute substantially to the overall biomass of the tree stand (Avery & Burkhart, 2002). The values of the BGB ranged from 12.64 to 40.15 kg/tree, with a mean of 23.00 kg/tree. In terms to root input to total biomass, the obtained values are predictable since root biomass is typically a fraction of the total tree biomass (Cairns et al., 1997).

The correlations among tree growth, biomass parameters, and soil nutrients properties in both soil layers are presented in Table 3. Only statistically significant correlations are discussed to highlight their substantial reciprocal interactions. TC is positively correlated with sand content in both the topsoil and subsoil. Studies revealed that soils were sandier under canopies of trees (Volkenhube et al., 2004), as water dripping from leaves of tree canopies could mobilize fine particles vertically or horizontally, leaving behind coarser sand contents. The importance of TC in this relationship is obvious, as it may influence the distribution of sand content through biomass turnover, litter inputs, and the canopy hydrological effects (Eni et al., 2012). TC correlated negatively with Ca and Mg at the topsoil. This may be due to the production of organic acids from decomposing litter of TC that can reduce the

quantities of Ca and Mg (Finzi et al., 1998). This may also account for the observed low and moderate status of Ca and Mg, respectively, in this study.

AGTB correlated positively with TH at the topsoil. This should be expected as TH is a significant predictor for AGTB. Jilo et al., (2025) noted that TH is a more important factor in determining biomass. Reciprocally, AGTB increases with TH, with taller trees often contributing meaningfully to the overall biomass of a wooded area. Fotis et al., (2018) reported that AGTB was improved in communities dominated by traits associated to greater TH. The findings of the current are consistent with those of Egeta et al., (2023), who reported that AGTB had a substantial correlation with TH for *Albizia dimidiata*. BGB correlated positively with TH, DBH, and AGTB in the topsoil, proposing that greater BGB

Table 3: Correlation matrix for topsoil (above the diagonal) and subsoil (below the diagonal) for soil quality indicators, tree growth, and biomass parameters.

	Sand	Silt	Clay	BD	TP	pH	TOC	SOM	CEC	TN	Avail P	Ca	Mg	Na	K	TH	DBH	TC	AGTB	BGB
Sand	1	-0.356	-0.456	0.256	-0.256	-0.454	0.213	0.212	-0.173	-0.169	0.119	-0.515	-0.456	-0.142	-0.106	0.503	0.318	0.726*	0.506	0.506
Silt	-0.531	1	-0.670*	0.145	-0.145	0.552	0.209	0.209	-0.398	0.516	-0.039	0.794**	0.800**	-0.707*	-0.474	0.017	-0.073	-0.613	0.019	0.019
Clay	-0.437	-0.531	1	-0.341	0.341	-0.165	-0.368	-0.367	0.516	-0.357	-0.057	-0.347	-0.399	0.785*	0.535	-0.415	-0.184	0.007	-0.419	-0.420
BD	-0.189	0.040	0.147	1	-1.000**	-0.064	-0.060	-0.059	-0.386	0.373	-0.057	-0.069	-0.034	0.154	-0.392	-0.438	-0.422	0.448	-0.478	-0.478
TP	0.189	-0.040	-0.147	-1.000**	1	0.064	0.060	0.059	0.386	-0.373	0.057	0.069	0.034	-0.154	0.392	0.438	0.422	-0.448	0.478	0.478
pH	-0.562	0.704	-0.185	0.347	-0.347	1	0.495	0.495	0.348	0.249	0.066	0.735**	0.700*	-0.148	0.268	-0.418	0.282	-0.515	-0.257	-0.258
TOC	0.326	-0.614	0.326	-0.095	0.095	-0.416	1	1.000**	0.592	0.408	0.117	0.498	0.502	-0.452	0.560	0.001	0.427	-0.008	0.112	0.112
SOM	0.326	-0.615	0.326	-0.096	0.095	-0.417	1.000**	1	0.593	0.409	0.117	0.499	0.502	-0.451	0.560	0.000	0.426	-0.008	0.111	0.110
CEC	-0.139	-0.662	0.842**	0.006	-0.006	-0.326	0.740*	0.740*	1	0.059	0.183	0.107	0.052	0.259	0.994**	-0.326	0.233	0.021	-0.237	-0.238
TN	0.203	0.235	-0.452	0.174	-0.174	0.111	0.461	0.460	-0.137	1	0.495	0.337	0.344	-0.429	0.036	-0.116	-0.448	0.074	-0.236	-0.236
Avail P	-0.414	0.754*	-0.386	-0.151	0.151	0.765*	-0.536	-0.537	-0.557	0.031	1	-0.335	-0.381	-0.132	0.235	0.201	-0.299	0.372	0.046	0.046
Ca	0.056	-0.500	0.475	0.262	-0.262	-0.566	0.366	0.366	0.439	0.078	-0.817*	1	0.985**	-0.513	0.005	-0.261	0.169	-0.778*	-0.150	-0.150
Mg	-0.009	-0.380	0.413	0.197	-0.197	-0.532	0.319	0.319	0.338	0.167	-0.688	0.972**	1	-0.519	-0.049	-0.191	0.248	-0.717*	-0.060	-0.060
Na	0.175	-0.085	-0.084	0.075	-0.075	-0.451	-0.186	-0.187	-0.289	0.031	-0.066	0.188	0.300	1	0.284	-0.548	-0.106	0.349	-0.491	-0.491
K	-0.154	-0.628	0.820*	-0.013	0.013	-0.261	0.732*	0.732*	0.995**	-0.143	-0.509	0.372	0.264	-0.374	1	-0.276	0.219	0.103	-0.203	-0.203
TH	0.551	-0.156	-0.385	-0.703*	0.703*	-0.365	0.566	0.566	0.063	0.463	-0.109	-0.094	-0.062	-0.204	0.082	1	0.384	0.144	0.954**	0.955**
DBH	-0.073	-0.037	0.113	-0.195	0.195	0.440	0.421	0.420	0.298	0.245	0.286	-0.237	-0.234	-0.705*	0.362	0.384	1	-0.062	0.637*	0.636*
TC	0.671*	-0.451	-0.192	0.329	-0.329	-0.284	0.260	0.260	0.057	0.125	-0.652*	0.341	0.170	-0.257	0.061	0.144	-0.062	1	0.088	0.088
AGTB	0.424	-0.136	-0.279	-0.631*	0.631*	-0.168	0.621	0.621	0.150	0.499	-0.007	-0.121	-0.086	-0.372	0.183	0.954**	0.637*	0.088	1	1.000**
BGB	0.424	-0.136	-0.280	-0.631*	0.631*	-0.169	0.621	0.621	0.150	0.500	-0.007	-0.121	-0.085	-0.372	0.183	0.955**	0.636*	0.088	1.000**	1

** = correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed), * = correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Source: Authors' Fieldwork, 2025

is related to increased tree size and productivity, and highlighting their mutual roles in maintaining and supporting *Terminalia mantaly* functionality.

TH correlated negatively with BD but positively with TP at the subsoil. BD is considered as a significant factor influencing soil nutrients as well as soil compactness (Al-Shammary et al., 2018). By contrast, TP primarily facilitates the transport of soil water, soil gases exchange, and soil nutrients movement and storage (Shen et al., 2022). The results suggested that *Terminalia mantaly* are likely to grow taller where the subsoil is less compact and more porous. The finding also highlights the strong association between the growth of tree as well as the physical properties of subsoil. The findings of this study are not consistent with those of Ndakara (2024), who reported positive correlations between TH and both BD and TP. DBH correlated negatively with Mg in the subsoil, implying that lower Mg availability in the subsoil may limit the growth of *Terminalia mantaly* trees. TC correlated positively with sand but negatively with Avail. P in the subsoil, suggesting that *Terminalia mantaly* trees tend to have larger canopies in soils with higher sand content and lower Avail. P in the subsoil. AGTB correlated positively with TP, TH, and DBH, but negatively with BD in the subsoil. These results suggested that the aboveground biomass of *Terminalia mantaly* tends to be higher in soils with greater total porosity, larger trees with greater DBH, and less compacted soils. The results aligned with those of Ononyume and Edu (2025), who reported a strong positive correlation between DBH and AGTB. BGB correlated positively with TP, TH, DBH, and AGTB, but negatively with BD in the subsoil, demonstrating that the belowground biomass of *Terminalia mantaly* tends to be higher in soils with greater total

porosity, larger trees, greater aboveground biomass, and less compacted soils.

Quite strikingly, *Terminalia mantaly* growth and biomass parameters showed more significant relationships with subsoil properties than with topsoil properties, suggesting that the subsoil plays a stronger role in the species' growth.

CONCLUSION

AND

RECOMMENDATIONS

The research investigated urban roadside topsoil and subsoil nutrients under the canopy of *Terminalia mantaly*. In addition, the relationships among tree growth, biomass, and soil quality indicators were also examined. The findings indicated that values of sand, silt, TP, pH, CEC, SOM, TOC, TN, Avail. P, Ca, Mg, and K were higher in the topsoil, whereas clay, BD, and Na were higher in the subsoil. Significant differences between the topsoil and subsoil were observed only for sand, clay, SOM, TOC, Ca, and Mg. The results further revealed significant relationships among tree growth, biomass, and soil quality indicators at both soil depths and showed that tree growth and biomass are more substantially connected with subsoil properties than with topsoil properties. The research concluded that the differences in soil quality indicators' levels between the topsoil and subsoil are ascribed to the impacts of human activities along the roadside and the *Terminalia mantaly* canopy, and that the role of subsoil in the growth and development of the tree species is significant. The study recommended the application of organic amendments to the topsoil and that the monitoring and management of subsoil be integrated into urban roadside soil conservation policies. Future research should focus on the microbial properties of urban roadside soils.

REFERENCES

- Adedeji, G. A., Eguakun, F. S., Egubogo, A. C., & Aiyeloja, A. A. (2022). Insecurities: Special focus on *Terminalia mantaly* H. Perrier use in Nigeria. In O. Y. Ogunsanwo, N. A. Adewole, P. I. Oni, & I. O. Azeez (Eds.), *Securing Nigeria's forest estate for sustainable development: Proceedings of the 43rd Annual Conference of the Forestry Association of Nigeria, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria, 14–18 March 2022* (pp. 365–370). Forestry Association of Nigeria.
- Adejuwon, J. O., & Adesina, F. A. (1990). *Organic matter and nutrient status of soils under cultivated fallows: An example of Gliricidia sepium fallows from south-western Nigeria. Agroforestry Systems, 10, 23–32.*
- Akinde, B.P., Olakayode, A. O., Oyedele, D. J., & Tijani, F.O. (2020). Selected physical and chemical properties of soil under different agricultural land-use types in Ile-Ife, Nigeria. *Heliyon, 6, 1 – 9.*
- Alo, E.A., & Aweto, A.O. (2018). The properties of soil under the canopy of the locust bean tree (*Parkia biglobosa*), in relation to tree biomass, in farmland in Oyo Area, South Western Nigeria. *Journal of Environment and Earth Science, 8 (8), 38-46.*
- Al-Shammary, A. A. G., Kouzani, A. Z., Kaynak, A., Khoo, S. Y., Norton, M., & Gates, W. (2018). Soil bulk density estimation methods: A review. *Pedosphere 28, 581–596.*
- Arifin, A., Karam, D.S., Shamshuddin, J., Majid, N.M., Radziah, O., Hazandy, A.H., & Zahari, I. (2012). Proposing a suitable soil quality index for natural, secondary and rehabilitated tropical forests in Malaysia. *African Journal of Biotechnology, 11, 3297 – 3309.*
- Atewe, F.A., & Asikhia, M.O. (2025). Spatial variability of urban public transportation fare and the trigger factors in the Benin Metropolis, Nigeria. *Case Studies on Transport Policy, 21, 101553.* doi.org/10.1016/j.cstp.2025.101553.
- Avery, T. E., & Burkhart, H. E. (2002). *Forest measurements* (5th ed.). McGraw-Hill.
- Aweto, A. O. (1981a). Secondary succession and soil fertility restoration in south-western Nigeria. *Journal of Ecology, 69, 957 – 963.*
- Aweto, A.O. (1981b). Organic matter build-up in fallow soil in a part of south-western Nigeria and its effects on soil properties. *Journal of Biogeography, 8, 67-74.*
- Babalola, F. D., & Raji, I. A. (2016). Perception of urban trees at main campus of University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria. *Applied Tropical Agriculture, 21(1), 60-67.*
- Begum, F., Bajracharya, R. M., Sharma, S., & Sitaula, B. K. (2010). *Influence of slope aspect on soil physico-chemical and biological properties in the mid hills of central Nepal. International Journal of Sustainable Development & World Ecology, 17(5), 438–443.*
- Cairns, M. A., Brown, S., Helmer, E. H., & Baumgardner, G. A. (1997). Root biomass allocation in the world's upland forests. *Oecologia, 111, 1-11.*
- Chave, J., Andalo, C., Brown, S., Cairns, M. A., Chambers, J. Q., Eamus, D., Fölster, H., Fromard, F., Higuchi, N., Kira, T., Lescure, J.-P., Nelson, B. W., Ogawa, H., Puig, H., Riera, B., & Yamakura, T. (2005). *Tree allometry and improved estimation of*

carbon stocks and balance in tropical forests. *Oecologia*, 145(1), 87–99.

Chen, Y., Rademacher, T., Fonti, P., Eckes-Shephard, A. H., LeMoine, J. M., Fonti, M. V., Richardson, A. D., & Friend, A. D. (2022). Inter-annual and inter-species tree growth explained by phenology of xylogenesis. *New Phytologist*, 235(3), 939–952.

Craul, P. J., & Klein, C. J. (1980). Characterization of street side soils in Syracuse, New York. Metropolitan Tree Improvement Alliance (METRIA). *Proceedings* 3, 88–101.

Craul, P. J., & Patterson, J. C. (1989). The urban soil as a rooting environment. In *Proceedings of the Fourth National Urban Forestry Conference* (pp. 97–102).

Demessie, A., Singh, B., & Lal, R. (2011). Soil carbon and nitrogen stocks under plantations in Gambo District, Southern Ethiopia. *Journal of Sustainable Forestry*, 30, 496 – 517.

Ebele, O.P., Treasure, U.N., Gerald, U.W., & Ebere, C.C. (2021). Phytochemical screening and antimicrobial evaluation of ethanol extract and fractions of the leaf of *Terminalia mantaly* H. Perrier (Combretaceae). *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, 10(3), 07-10.

Edmondson, J.L., O’Sullivan, O.S., Inger, R., Potter, J., & McHugh, N. (2014). Urban tree effects on soil organic carbon. *PLoS ONE*, 9(7):e101872.doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0101872.

Egeta, D., Negash, M., Alebachew, M., Eshete, A., Mulugeta, S., & Lemi, T. (2023). Species-specific allometric equations, biomass expansion factor, and wood density

of native tree species in the dry Afromontane Forest of Ethiopia. *International Journal of Forestry Research*, 5572048, 1-11.

Ekanade, O., & Orimoogunje, O. O. I. (2012). *Application of canonical correlation for soil-vegetation interrelationship in the cocoa belt of South Western Nigeria. Resources and Environment*, 2(3), 87–92.

Ekpenkhio, E., Odjugo, P.A.O., Ugwa, I.K., Orobator, P.O., & Asikhia, M.O. (2025). Public perception and experience of urban land use soil pollution risks in Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Environmental Sciences and Technology*, 9(1), 13-24.

Eludoyin, O.S., Oladele, A.T., & Iyanda, O.M. (2015). Mapping and assessment of ethno-medicinal trees in built up areas - University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *South-east European Forestry*, 6 (1), 129-140.

Eni, D. D. Iwara, A. I., & Offiong, R.A. (2012). Analysis of soil-vegetation interrelationships a South-Southern Secondary Forest of Nigeria. *International Journal of Forestry Research*, 469326, 1-8.

Finzi, A.C., Canham, C.D. & Breemen, N.V. (1998). Canopy tree-soil interactions within temperate forests: species effects on pH and cations. *Ecological Applications*, 8(2), 447–454.

Fotis, A.T., Murphy, S.J., Ricart, R.D., Krishnadas, M., Whitacre, J., Wenzel, J.W., Queenborough, S.A., & Comita, L.S. (2018). Above-ground biomass is driven by mass-ratio effects and stand structural attributes in a temperate deciduous forest. *Journal of Ecology*, 106, 561–570.

- Gallardo, D.A. (2003). Effect of tree canopy on the spatial distribution of soil nutrients in a Mediterranean. *Pedobiologia* 47, 117–125.
- Gee, G. W., & Or, D. (2002). Particle-size analysis. In J. H. Dane & G. C. Topp (Eds.), *Methods of Soil Analysis, Part 4: Physical Methods* (pp. 255–293). Soil Science Society of America.
- Guilland, C., Maron, P. A., Damas, O., & Ranjard, L. (2018). Biodiversity of urban soils for sustainable cities. *Environmental Chemistry Letters*, 16(4), 1267–1282.
- Haan, F. A. M., & van der Valk, G. G. M. (1970). Effects of soil compaction, restricted aeration, and frost injury on flower bulb crops: I. Effects of compaction on physical properties of soil and root growth of ornamental bulbs. In *Proceedings of the 1st International Symposium on Flower Bulbs* (pp. 326–332).
- Hamza, H., Shehu, B. M., & Sani, S. (2025). The Effect of land usage and depth on soil quality in Northern Nigeria's Semi-Arid Region. *FUDMA Journal of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology*, 11, 3, 37-53.
- Han, G., Huo, J., Hu, R., Gong, X., Nan, Y., Lian, Y. & Zhang, Z. (2025). Coupling relationships between vegetation and soil in different vegetation types in the Ulan Buh Desert and the Kubuqi Desert. *Front. Plant Science*, 16, 1505526.
- He, C., Jiang, W., Wang, T., Yuan, D., & Sha, A. (2024). The evolution of tire-road wear particles and road surface texture under rolling friction. *Construction and Building Materials*, 447. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.138167>.
- Hilbert, D., Roman, L., Koeser, A., Vogt, J., & van Doorn, N. (2019). Urban tree mortality: A literature review. *Arboriculture & Urban Forestry*, 45, (5), 167-200.
- Ichikogu, V. I. (2014). Relationships between soil and vegetation structural properties of secondary forest regenerating in degraded rubber plantation in the Niger Delta Area of Nigeria. *African Review Research*, 8(3), 123-139.
- Isola, J. O., Asunlegan O. A., Abiodun, F. O. & Smart, M. O. (2020). Effect of soil depth and topography on physical and chemical properties of soil along Federal College of Forestry, Ibadan North West, Oyo State. *Journal of Research in Forestry, Wildlife and Environment*, 12, 2, 382-390.
- Iwara, A.I. (2011). Multivariate analysis of soil-vegetation interrelationships in a south-southern secondary forest of Nigeria. *International Journal of Biology*, 3 (3), 73-82.
- Jilo, D., Birhane, E., Tadesse, T. & Ubuy, M.H. (2025). Aboveground biomass models for common woody species of lowland forest in Borana Woodland, Southern Ethiopia. *Forests*. 16, 823, 1-20.
- Jim, C. Y. (1998). Physical and chemical properties of a Hong Kong roadside soil in relation to urban tree growth *Urban Ecosystems*, 2, 171–181.
- Jim, C.Y., & Ng, Y.Y. (2018). Porosity of roadside soil as indicator of edaphic quality for tree planting. *Ecological Engineering* 120, 364–374.
- Jimoh, I.A., Mbaya, L.A., Akande, D., Agaku, T.A., & Haruna, S. (2020). Impact of toposequence on soil properties and classification in Zaria Kaduna State, Northern Guinea Savanna, Nigeria. *EQA* –

International Journal of Environmental Quality, 38, 48 – 58.

Joimel, S., Cortet, J., Jolivet, C. C., Saby, N. P. A., Chenot, E. D., Branchu, P., Consalès, J., Lefort, C., Morel, J., & Schwartz, C. (2016). Physico-chemical characteristics of topsoil for contrasted forest, agricultural, urban and industrial land uses in France. *Science of the Total Environment*, 54, 40–47.

Kamal, A., Mian, I. A., Akbar, W. A., Rahim, H. U., Irfan, M., Ali, S., Alrefael, A. F., Zaman, W. (2023). Effects of soil depth and altitude on soil texture and soil quality index. *Applied Ecology and Environmental Research*, 21, (5), 4135-4154.

Kavane, R. P. & Chougale T.M. (2024). *Terminalia Mantaly* H. Perrier. - A potential new host of Tropical Tasar silkworm, *Antheraea Mylitta* Drury (Lepidoptera-Saturniidae). *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews*, 11 (3), 418-425.

Kim, Y.J. & Yoo, G. (2021). Suggested key variables for assessment of soil quality in urban roadside tree systems. *Journal of Soils and Sediments*. 21, 2130–2140.

Koptsik, S. V., Koptsik, G. N., Livantsova, S. Y., Berezina, N. A., & Vakhrameeva, M. G. (2003). Analysis of the relationship between soil and vegetation in forest biogeocenoses by the principal component method. *Russian Journal of Ecology*, 34, 34–42.

Kurniawan, S., Utami, S. R., Mukharomah, M., Navarette, I. A., & Prasetya, B. (2019). Land use systems, soil texture, control carbon and nitrogen storages in the forest soil of UB forest, Indonesia. – AGRIVITA, *Journal of Agricultural Science*, 41, 416-427.

Landon, J. R. (1991). *Booker tropical soil manual: A handbook for soil survey and agricultural land evaluation in the tropics and subtropics*. Essex: Addison Wesley Longman Limited, pp 472.

Levine, E.R., Knox, R.G., & Lawrence, W.T. (1994). Relationships between soil properties and vegetation at the Northern Experimental Forest, Howland, Maine. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 47, 2, 231-241.

Mafuyai, G. M., Kamoh, N. M., Kangpe, N. S., Ayuba, S.M., & Eneji, I. S. (2015). Heavy metals contamination in roadside dust along major traffic roads in Jos Metropolitan Area. *Nigeria European Journal of Earth and Environment*, 2 (1), 1-14.

Mashagiro, G.Q., Mujinya, B.B., Colinet, G., & Mahy, G. (2024) Vegetation degradation alters soil physicochemical properties and potentially affects ecosystem services in green spaces of a tropical megacity (Lubumbashi, DR Congo). *Geoderma Regional*, 37,1-9.

Mengistu, C., Kibebew, K., & Tarekegn, F. (2017). Influence of different land use types and soil depths on selected soil properties related to soil fertility in Warandhab Area, Horo Guduru Wallaga Zone, Oromiya, Ethiopia. *International Journal of Environmental Sciences and Natural Resources*,4(2), 68-78.

Miller, A. T., Allen, H. L., & Maier, C. A. (2006). *Quantifying the coarse-root biomass of intensively managed loblolly pine plantations*. *Canadian Journal of Forest Research*, 36(1), 12–22.

Ndakara, O.E. (2024). Correlation analyses of measures of plant biomass and soil attributes under bush mango and lowland rainforest

trees in Nigeria. *Global Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences*, 30,127-134.

Norris, C. E., Hogg, K. E., Maynard, D. G., & Curran, M. P. (2014). Stumping trials in British Columbia-organic matter removal and compaction effects on tree growth from seedlings to midrotation stands. *Canadian Journal of Forest Research*, 44, 1402–1418.

Nwosu, T., Okenmuo, F., Nweke, I.A., Igboka, C.R., Anene, C.K., & Chukwuma, T.R. (2025). Interactive effect of land use types and depth on selected physicochemical properties of soils: A case study. *Nova Geodesia*, 5 (1), 261.

Odegbaro, D. O. O., & Aweto, A. O. (2017). *Soil and vegetation dynamics and interrelationships in bush fallow of the derived savanna of Oyo area, south-western Nigeria. Nigerian Geographical Journal*, 11, 147–166.

Ogunkunle, O. (2013). A comparative study of the physical and chemical properties of soils under different vegetation types. *Journal of Environment and Earth Science*, 3, (1), 24-38.

Ononyume, M. O. & Edu, E.A.B. (2025). Assessment of growth, biomass, and carbon sequestration potential of three urban tree species in Calabar. *Journal of Wildlife and Biodiversity*, 9 (3), 436-449.

Orobator, P. O., & Adahwara, P. O. (2022). *Estimation of carbon storage and sequestration by tropical urban trees in Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria. Nigerian Journal of Environmental Sciences and Technology*, 6(1), 214–224.

Orobator, P. O., & Daniel, A. (2025). Assessment of potentially toxic elements contamination in soils across different land uses in a rural-urban fringe area of Edo State. *Aswan University Journal of Environmental Studies (AUJES)*, 6 (2), 108-125.

Owoade, O.M. & Oke, D. G. (2020). Chemical composition of the essential oils from the leaf, stem-bark and twig of *Terminalia mantaly* H. Perrier (Combretaceae) from Nigeria. *European Journal of Advanced Chemistry Research*, 1 (5), 1-4.

Panthi, S., Mandal, R.A., & Mathema, A. B. (2022). Correlation of tree diameter, height and biodiversity with soil N, P and K. *American Journal of Life Sciences*, 10, (6),123-130.

Parthiban, K.T. & Rai, R.S.V. (1994). Trees on farmlands –their effects on soil fertility. *Annals of Forestry*, 2(1), 44-51.

Qi, S. (2024). *Trees in urban environments: How soil quality impacts tree performance* (Doctoral dissertation, The City University of New York).

Qin, G., Wu, J., Zheng, X., Zhou, R., & Wei, Z. (2019). Phosphorus forms and associated properties along an urban–rural gradient in Southern China. *Water*, 11, 1-11.

Redin, C., Valente, M.L., Andriollo, D.D., Junior, A.V.L., de Araújo, E.F., Reichert, J.M. (2023). Soil-landscape-vegetation relationships in grassland-forest boundaries, and possible applications in ecological restoration. *Journal of South American Earth Sciences*, 132, 104684.

- Sager, M. (2020). Environments urban soils and road dust—civilization effects and metal pollution—A Review. *Environments*, 7, 98.1-65.
- Sahrawat, K.L. (2004). Organic matter accumulation in submerged soils. *Advances in Agronomy* 81,169-201.
- Samuel, B., & Adekunle, Y.A. (2021). Isolation and structure elucidation of anti-malarial principles from *Terminalia mantaly* H. Perrier stem bark. *International Journal of Biological and Chemical Sciences*, 15(1), 282-292.
- Säumel, I., Weber, F., & Kowarik, I. (2016). Toward livable and healthy urban streets: roadside vegetation provides ecosystem services where people live and move. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 62, 24–33.
- Shen, Y.F., Li, J., Chen, F.F., Cheng, R.M., Xiao, W.F., Wu, L.C. & Zeng, L.X. (2022). Correlations between forest soil quality and aboveground vegetation characteristics in Hunan Province, China. *Frontiers in Plant Science*,13, 1-13.
- Spurr, H. R., & Barnes, B. V. (1980). *Forest ecology* (3rd ed.). John Wiley.
- Teramage, M. T., Asfaw, M., Demissie, A., Feyissa, A., Ababu, T., Gonfa, Y., & Sime, G. (2023). Effects of land use types on the depth distribution of selected soil properties in two contrasting agro-climatic zones. *Heliyon*, 9, (6), 1-14.
- Ubom, R. M., & Isichei, A. O. (1995). Soil-vegetation interrelationships in Isoberlinia woodlands of Northwestern Nigeria. *Acta Botanica Hungarica*, 39(3-4).
- Ubuoh, E.A., Akhionbare, W.N., Onweremadu, E., & Onifade, O.A. (2013). Characterization of soil quality in erosion prone environment of Ukpok, Nnewi-South L.G.A. of Anambra State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Advances in Applied Sciences (IJAAS)* 2(1), 1-8.
- Ukpong, I. E., & Areola, O. O. (1995). Relationship between vegetation gradients and soil variables of mangrove swamps in south-eastern Nigeria. *African Journal of Ecology*, 33,14–24.
- Usman, B. M., Attah, D. D.-I., & Kanya, D. Y. (2022). Preliminary phytochemical analysis and invitro antiplasmodial activity of *Terminalia mantaly* against plasmodium falciparum. *Folia Medica Indonesiana*, 58(4), 318–324.
- van Noordwijk, M., & Purnomosidhi, P. (1995). Root architecture in relation to tree-soil-crop interaction and shoot pruning in agroforestry. *Agroforestry Systems*, 30, 161–173.
- Volkenhube, J.A., Enquist, B.J, West, G.P., & Brown , J.H. (2004). Extension and evaluations of a general quantitative theory of forest structure and dynamics. *PNAS*, 106, 17, 7046- 7051.
- Wang, H. F., & López-Pujol, J. (2015). Urban green spaces and plant diversity at different spatial–temporal scales: A case study from Beijing. *Collectanea Botanica*, 34(e008), 1–8.
- Werkenthin, M., Kluge, B., & Wessolek, G. (2014). Metals in European roadside soils and soil solution – A review, *Environmental Pollution*, 189, 98-110.
- Yahqub, M., Jimoh, A.I., & Owonubi, A. (2024). Evaluation of land use impact on soil quality in Samaru College of Agriculture, Northern Guinea Savanna, Nigeria.

Agricultura Tropica Et Subtropica, 57, 35–44.

Young, A. (2000). *Agroforestry for soil conservation* (2nd ed.). CAB International.

Yunusa, A.Y., Yakasai, M.A., & Namadina, M.M. (2024). Evaluation of phytochemical composition, antioxidant activity, and antibacterial properties of *Terminalia mantaly* H. Perrier Leaf Extract. *Dutse Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences (DUJOPAS)*, 10,(4), 60- 69.